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MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF CARDIAC CYCLE USING LUMPED PARAMETER METHOD

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Abstract:

This work reviews the main aspects of cardiovascular system dynamics with an emphasis on modeling hemodynamic characteristics by the use of a lumped parameter approach. This model describes relationships between flow rate and pressure using electric circuit models based on analogy between blood flow and pressure of the cardiovascular system and the current and voltage in an electrical circuit system.

A mathematical model of pumping heart coupled to lumped compartments of blood circulation is presented in this paper. This lumped pulsatile cardiovascular model consists of eight compartments of the body that include pumping heart, the systemic circulation and the pulmonary circulation. The governing equations for the pressure and flow in each compartment are derived from the following three equations: Ohm's law, conservation of volume and the definition of compliances. The four chambers, two arteries and two veins are connected by the time varied activated functions for pumping heart.

This paper is an attempt to explain a simple cardiovascular circulation model, in order to investigate pressure change in each compartment during seven phases over one cardiac cycle.

Keywords: *Cardiovascular system, lumped parameters, Electrical analogy, blood vessels, cardiac phases*

Introduction:

Lumped parameter model is a very useful type of mathematical modeling which simplifies the description of the behaviour of spatially distributed physical systems into an electric network which approximate the behaviour of the physical system under certain assumptions. Lumped parameter model is represented graphically by an equivalent electric circuit diagram in which the vertices represent the voltages and the edges the current in the diagram. The mathematical analysis of such a circuit model is very convenient and makes it easy to analyse the actual physical system. These models are constructed by building the analogy between blood flow and blood pressure with electrical current and electrical voltage respectively. This

analogy is interpreted using simple ordinary differential equations in time which can be solved either numerically or analytically.

Analogy between Cardiovascular system and Electrical Network – determination of:

<u>Cardio vascular system</u>	≈	<u>Electric circuit</u>
Blood pressure	≈	Voltage
Blood flow	≈	Current
Volume of blood	≈	Charge
Blood vessel resistance	≈	Resistance
Compliance	≈	Capacitance
Valves	≈	Diodes

The heart consists of four chambers namely right atrium (RA), left atrium (LA), right ventricle (RV) and left ventricle (LV) and four valves namely tricuspid valve (Tr), pulmonary valve (Pu), mitral valve (Mi) and the aortic valve (Ao). Systemic arteries (sa), systemic veins (sv), pulmonary arteries (pa), and pulmonary veins (pv) form the systemic and the pulmonary circulations. This can be schematically represented as follows [1], [2], [3].

Figure 1: Equivalent Circuit for Lumped Model

In the above diagram the symbols and their representation is as follows.

Symbol	Representation	Symbol	Representation
R _{pu}	resistance of pulmonary valve	R _{Ao}	resistance of Aortic valve
R _T	resistance of tricuspid valve	R _{Mi}	resistance of Mitral valve
R _{sv}	resistance of systemic vein	R _{pv}	resistance of pulmonary vein
C _{RV}	compliance of Right Ventricle	C _{RA}	compliance of Right Auricle
C _{LV}	compliance of Left Ventricle	C _{LA}	compliance of Left Auricle

Pressure exerted by the blood and volume of flow of blood in each compartment are studied using Ohm’s law, conservation of volume and the definition of compliances. It is important to note that the four chambers, two arteries and two veins are connected using time varied functions.

The resistance of blood flow can be represented by the ratios of pressure to flow. The relation between pressure and flow can be derived from Ohm’s law:

$$Q(t) = \frac{\Delta P(t)}{R} \text{-----(1)}$$

where Q(t) represents the blood flow, ΔP(t) represents the pressure difference between the successive compartments and R represents the constant flow resistance.

Rate of change of volume of blood in each compartment can be derived from the equation of volume conservation: $\frac{dV(t)}{dt} = Q_{in}(t) - Q_{out}(t)$ -----(2)

where V(t) is the volume of blood in each compartment , Q_{in}(t)= flow into the compartment and Q_{out}(t)= flow out of the compartment.

The volume compliance can be represented using capacitors. The compliance relation for each compartment can be derived from the relation:

$$V(t) = V_d + C(t) P(t) \text{-----(3)}$$

where V_d is the dead volume when the pressure is nil, C(t) the compliance and P(t) the pressure. It is obvious that the compliance is considered as a time dependent function in all the four chambers of heart. The following symbols are used for the different units of heart.

LA	left auricle	RA	right auricle
LV	left ventricle	RV	right ventricle
pv	pulmonary vein	pa	pulmonary artery
sv	systemic vein	sa	systemic artery

At the other considered parts of circulation i.e., pulmonary vein (pv), pulmonary artery (pa), systemic vein (sv) and systemic artery (sa), the compliance is considered to possess a constant value.

The modeling of cardiac valves is done using step function $S(t)$, and the step function for cardiac valves are represented as $S_{Mi}(t)$ for mitral valve, $S_{Tr}(t)$ for tricuspid valve, $S_{Ao}(t)$ for pulmonary valve and $S_{Pu}(t)$ for pulmonary valve and defined as follows. Here P represents the pressure and the subscript represents the respective compartment in the heart system as indicated above.

$$S_{Mi}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } P_{LA} \geq P_{LV} \\ 0 & \text{if } P_{LA} < P_{LV} \end{cases}$$

$$S_{Tr}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } P_{RA} \geq P_{RV} \\ 0 & \text{if } P_{RA} < P_{RV} \end{cases}$$

$$S_{Ao}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } P_{LV} \geq P_{sa} \\ 0 & \text{if } P_{LV} < P_{sa} \end{cases}$$

$$S_{Pu}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } P_{RV} \geq P_{pa} \\ 0 & \text{if } P_{RV} < P_{pa} \end{cases}$$

where P_{LA} represents the pressure in Left Atrium, P_{LV} represents the pressure in Left Ventricle, P_{RA} represents the pressure in Right Atrium, P_{RV} represents the pressure in Right Ventricle.

The above mentioned step function ensures the unidirectional flow of blood by preventing the reversal flow. If these step functions are not applied, then unidirectional blood flow is not ensured which means to say there will be mixing of pure and impure blood. In such a case the flow of blood will be a turbulent flow instead of laminar flow.

The main focus of the present study is on the cardiovascular system only, wherein different layers of blood will not come into picture within the scope of study. Therefore, the effects of viscosity are not considered for the current study. However, it is to be noted that viscosity of blood will have a significant role elsewhere in the circulatory system.

Substituting equations (1) and (3) in equation (2) and introducing step function, we get the following eight ordinary differential equations (ODEs) for the pressures have been derived [1], [2]:

$$\frac{d(C_{LA}(t)P_{LA}(t))}{dt} = \frac{P_{pv}(t) - P_{LA}(t)}{R_{pv}} - \frac{S_{Mi}(t)(P_{LA}(t) - P_{LV}(t))}{R_{Mi}}$$

$$\frac{d(C_{LV}(t)P_{LV}(t))}{dt} = \frac{S_{Mi}(t)(P_{LA}(t) - P_{LV}(t))}{R_{Mi}} - \frac{S_{Ao}(t)(P_{LV}(t) - P_{sa}(t))}{R_{Ao}}$$

$$\frac{C_{sa} dP_{sa}(t)}{dt} = \frac{S_{Ao}(t)(P_{LV}(t) - P_{sa}(t))}{R_{Ao}} - \frac{P_{sa}(t) - P_{sv}(t)}{R_s}$$

$$\frac{C_{sv} dP_{sv}(t)}{dt} = \frac{P_{sa}(t) - P_{sv}(t)}{R_s} - \frac{P_{sv}(t) - P_{RA}(t)}{R_{sv}}$$

$$\frac{d(C_{RA}(t)P_{RA}(t))}{dt} = \frac{P_{sv}(t) - P_{RA}(t)}{R_{sv}} - \frac{S_{Tr}(t)(P_{RA}(t) - P_{RV}(t))}{R_{Tr}}$$

$$\frac{d(C_{RV}(t)P_{RV}(t))}{dt} = \frac{S_{Tr}(t)(P_{RA}(t) - P_{RV}(t))}{R_{Tr}} - \frac{S_{Pu}(t)(P_{RV}(t) - P_{pa}(t))}{R_{Pu}}$$

$$\frac{C_{pa}dP_{pa}(t)}{dt} = \frac{S_{Pu}(t)(P_{RV}(t) - P_{pa}(t))}{R_{Pu}} - \frac{P_{pa}(t) - P_{pv}(t)}{R_p}$$

$$\frac{C_{pv}dP_{pv}(t)}{dt} = \frac{P_{pa}(t) - P_{pv}(t)}{R_p} - \frac{P_{pv}(t) - P_{LA}(t)}{R_{pv}}$$

The time-dependent compliances are used as a pumping source in this model.

The instantaneous volume is given by $V(t) = V_d + C(t)P(t)$; the definition of compliances has been used to activate the heart. The backward Euler’s method is used to solve the above mentioned system of ODEs.

Each individual cardiac cycle is divided into seven phases [4], [5], [6].

- Phase I: Atrial contraction
- Phase II: Isovolumetric contraction
- Phase III: Rapid ejection
- Phase IV: Reduced ejection
- Phase V: Isovolumetric relaxation
- Phase VI: Rapid filling
- Phase VII: Reduced filling

In the beginning of the cycle, the initial values for pressures at the eight compartments, as per the available information from literature [1], are chosen as follows: $P_{LA} = 10$, $P_{LV} = 9.8$, $P_{sa} = 100$, $P_{sv} = 5$, $P_{RA} = 5$, $P_{RV} = 4.8$, $P_{pa} = 20$ and $P_{pv} = 10$. The approximate time period of one cardiac cycle is $T=0.0133$ min [6]. For computational purpose the time step Δt is chosen as $\Delta t= (0.01)(T)$ min=0.000133 min.

The physiological resting values of constant compliances, resistances and dead volumes at each compartment are chosen as follows in Table 1. These values are based on the literature [1].

Compartment	Initial value of pressure (mm Hg)	Compartment	Initial value of resistance (mmHg/liter/min)	Compartment	Initial value of Capacitance (liter/mmHg)	Compartment	Value of the dead Volume (liter)
LA	10	Mi	0.01	Sa	0.0018	LA	0.03
LV	9.8	Sa	16.964	Sv	0.7	LV	0.03
Sa	100	Ao	0.01	Pa	0.0046	RV	0.03
Sv	5	Sv	0.05	Pv	0.04	Sa	0.825
RA	5	Tr	0.01			Pa	0.038
RV	4.8	Pa	1.786			Sv	0

Pa	20	Pu	0.01			Pv	0
Pv	10	Pv	0.05				

Table 1: Initial values of pressure (mm/Hg), resistance (mmHg/liter/min), capacitance (liter/mmHg) and value of dead volume (liter) of eight compartments

Taking these values from Table 1 as initial values i.e., P_n , C_n , V_d and choosing the values of the step function accordingly from Table 2 and using the algorithm of backward Euler's method the next values at instant $n+1$ are found. That is, the values of P_{n+1} and C_{n+1} are found.

Phase	Phase description	Observations	Values of Step function
I	Atrial contraction	$P_{LA} > P_{LV}$, $P_{LV} < P_{sa}$, $P_{RA} > P_{RV}$ and $P_{RV} < P_{pa}$	$S_{Mi}=1$, $S_{Ao}=0$, $S_{Tr}=1$ and $S_{Pu}=0$
II	Isovolumetric contraction	$P_{LA} < P_{LV}$, $P_{LV} > P_{sa}$, $P_{RA} < P_{RV}$ and $P_{RV} > P_{pa}$	$S_{Mi}=0$, $S_{Ao}=1$, $S_{Tr}=0$ and $S_{Pu}=1$
III	Rapid ejection	$P_{LA} < P_{LV}$, $P_{LV} > P_{sa}$, $P_{RA} < P_{RV}$ and $P_{RV} > P_{pa}$	$S_{Mi}=0$, $S_{Ao}=1$, $S_{Tr}=0$ and $S_{Pu}=1$
IV	Reduced ejection	$P_{LA} = P_{LV}$, $P_{LV} < P_{sa}$, $P_{RA} = P_{RV}$ and $P_{RV} < P_{pa}$	$S_{Mi}=1$, $S_{Ao}=0$, $S_{Tr}=1$ and $S_{Pu}=0$
V	Isovolumetric relaxation	$P_{LA} = P_{LV}$, $P_{LV} < P_{sa}$, $P_{RA} = P_{RV}$ and $P_{RV} < P_{pa}$	$S_{Mi}=1$, $S_{Ao}=0$, $S_{Tr}=1$ and $S_{Pu}=0$
VI	Rapid filling	$P_{LA} > P_{LV}$, $P_{LV} < P_{sa}$, $P_{RA} > P_{RV}$ and $P_{RV} < P_{pa}$	$S_{Mi}=1$, $S_{Ao}=0$, $S_{Tr}=1$ and $S_{Pu}=0$
VII	Reduced filling	$P_{LA} > P_{LV}$, $P_{LV} < P_{sa}$, $P_{RA} > P_{RV}$ and $P_{RV} < P_{pa}$	$S_{Mi}=1$, $S_{Ao}=0$, $S_{Tr}=1$ and $S_{Pu}=0$

Table 2: Values of step functions during seven phases

Referring to the Tables 1 and 2 the calculations are done for each of the phases and the pressure (mm of Hg) at each compartment during seven phases are tabulated below.

PHASE I

Table 3: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase I

Time(mi n)→ Compar tment↓	0.000932- 0.001064	0.001065- 0.001197	0.001198- 0.001330	0.001331- 0.001463	0.001464- 0.001596	0.001597- 0.001729	0.001730- 0.001862
	Pressure (mm of Hg)↓						
LA	10.0396	10.0284	9.9942	10.0450	10.0801	10.0563	10.0341
Pv	10.0050	10.0065	10.0057	10.0081	10.0126	10.0153	10.0165
LV	9.9927	9.9797	10.0330	10.0206	10.0053	9.9978	9.9854
Sa	100.000	100.00	100.0000	100.0000	100.0000	100.0000	100.0000
Sv	4.9991	4.9993	4.9992	4.9992	4.9992	4.9992	4.9991
RA	5.0292	5.0428	4.9755	4.9882	5.0063	4.9942	4.9746
Pa	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000
RV	4.9810	4.9970	4.9975	4.9727	4.9442	4.9262	4.9138

PHASE I (Continued)

Table 4: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase I continued

PHASE II

Time(mi n)→ Compar tment↓	0- 0.000133	0.000134 -	0.000267 -	0.000400 -	0.000533 -	0.000666 -	0.000799 -
	0.000133	0.000266	0.000399	0.000532	0.000665	0.000798	0.000931
Pressure (mm of Hg)↓							
LA	10	9.9385	9.9796	10.0166	10.0408	10.0540	10.0487
Pv	10	9.9922	9.9914	9.993	9.9960	9.9996	10.0027
LV	9.8	9.8965	9.9345	9.9675	9.9934	10.0089	10.0003
Sa	100	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.0000	100.0000
Sv	5	4.9995	4.9992	4.999	4.9989	4.9989	4.9990
RA	5	4.9075	4.9178	4.9444	4.9706	4.9928	5.0121
Pa	20	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000	20.0000
RV	4.8	4.8561	4.8723	4.8899	4.9118	4.9364	4.9603

Table 5: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase II

PHASE III

Time(mi n)→ Compar tment↓	0.002793- 0.002926	0.002927- 0.003059	0.003060- 0.003192	0.003193- 0.003325	0.003326- 0.003458	0.003459- 0.003591
	Pressure (mm of Hg)↓					
LA	10.0169	9.44420	8.80790	8.3376	8.0672	7.9531
Pv	10.0186	9.98280	9.90950	9.8115	9.7027	9.5936
LV	99.3883	101.4840	104.2978	107.3399	110.4327	113.5101
Sa	99.3826	101.2336	103.9325	106.9337	110.0156	113.0935
Sv	4.9993	4.9980	4.9949	4.9903	4.9845	4.9780
RA	4.9990	4.6457	4.1860	3.7751	3.4704	3.2763
Pa	19.4945	19.9622	20.8144	21.9103	23.1236	24.3782

Time(mi n)→ Compar tment↓	0.001863- 0.001995	0.001996- 0.002128	0.002129- 0.002261	0.002262- 0.002394	0.002395- 0.002527	0.002528- 0.002660	0.002661 - 0.002793
	Pressure (mm of Hg)↓						
LA	10.0443	10.0375	10.0252	10.0168	10.0135	10.0142	10.0162
Pv	10.0182	10.0194	10.0198	10.0196	10.0192	10.0189	10.0187
LV	22.2575	44.8933	70.8937	88.4713	96.1599	98.7352	99.4829
Sa	31.5249	43.2997	67.6043	85.9839	94.9469	98.2836	99.3399
Sv	4.9991	4.9991	4.9992	4.9993	4.9993	4.9993	4.9993
RA	4.9929	5.0072	5.0149	5.0155	5.0113	5.0050	4.9989
Pa	10.3886	10.2492	12.7180	15.4280	17.4803	18.7355	19.3930
RV	7.0643	10.2010	13.5719	16.3653	18.1901	19.1697	19.6205
RV	19.5295	20.1239	21.1092	22.2893	23.5433	24.8121	

Table 6: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase III

PHASE III (Continued)

Time(min)→ Compartment ↓	0.003592- 0.003724	0.003725- 0.003857	0.003858- 0.00399	0.00400- 0.004123	0.004124- 0.004256
	Pressure (mm of Hg)↓				
LA	7.9342	7.9553	7.9743	7.9671	7.9242
Pv	9.4901	9.3944	9.3059	9.2224	9.1415
LV	116.5965	119.6616	122.7096	125.7358	128.7848
Sa	116.1789	119.2464	122.2968	125.3258	128.3725
Sv	4.9712	4.9643	4.9576	4.9512	4.9453
RA	3.1782	3.1577	3.1967	3.2783	3.3863
Pa	25.6375	26.8886	28.1295	29.3595	30.5836
RV	26.0730	27.3213	28.5586	29.7849	31.0069

Table 7: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase III continued

PHASE IV

Time(min)→ Compartment ↓	0.004 257- 0.004 389	0.0043 90- 0.0045 22	0.004 523- 0.004 655	0.0046 56- 0.0047 88	0.0047 89- 0.0049 21	0.0049 22- 0.0050 54	0.0050 55- 0.0051 87	0.005 188- 0.005 320
	Pressure (mm of Hg)↓							
LA	11.313	11.458	9.8120	8.5606	7.8624	7.5093	7.3879	7.4478
Pv	9.2769	9.4129	9.4378	9.3831	9.2883	9.1774	9.0658	8.9649
LV	14.1996	9.7706	9.1342	8.5896	7.9488	7.5028	7.3402	7.4116
Sa	128.373	128.373	128.373	128.373	128.373	128.373	128.373	128.373
Sv	4.9455	4.9494	4.9525	4.9535	4.9532	4.9520	4.9502	4.9478
RA	4.9946	5.9695	5.7595	5.2289	4.8632	4.6387	4.4667	4.3166
Pa	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837
RV	7.5398	4.8209	4.7773	5.0744	5.0825	4.8280	4.5385	4.3265

Table 8: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase IV

PHASE IV (Continued)

Time(min)→ Compa rtment ↓	0.0053	0.0054	0.0055	0.0057	0.005	0.005	0.0061	0.006
	21- 0.0054 53	54- 0.0055 86	87- 0.0057 19	20- 0.0058 52	853- 0.005 985	986- 0.006 118	19- 0.0062 51	252- 0.006 384
Pressure (mm of Hg)↓								
LA	7.6492	7.9443	8.2778	8.5936	8.8424	8.9920	9.0322	8.9745
Pv	8.8829	8.8244	8.7903	8.7780	8.7820	8.7951	8.8099	8.8202
LV	7.6418	7.9646	8.3213	8.6550	8.9159	9.0710	9.1107	9.0476
Sa	128.373	128.373	128.373	128.373	128.373	128.373	128.373	128.373
Sv	4.9450	4.9419	4.9387	4.9355	4.9325	4.9299	4.9277	4.9259
RA	4.1964	4.1190	4.0890	4.1035	4.1558	4.2381	4.3419	4.4577
Pa	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837
RV	4.1978	4.1303	4.1088	4.1272	4.1822	4.2689	4.3788	4.5015

Table 9: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase IV continued

PHASE V

Time(min)→ Compa rtment ↓	0.006385	0.006518	0.006652	0.006785	0.006918	0.007052	0.007185
	- 0.006517	- 0.006651	- 0.006784	- 0.006917	- 0.007051	- 0.007184	- 0.007317
Pressure (mm of Hg)↓							
LA	8.8605	8.7107	8.5547	8.4164	8.3090	8.2375	8.2006
Pv	8.8227	8.8157	8.7994	8.7755	8.7464	8.7147	8.6826
LV	8.8854	8.7140	8.5528	8.4119	8.3014	8.2280	8.1907
Sa	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728
Sv	4.9246	4.9238	4.9234	4.9233	4.9234	4.9235	4.9236
RA	4.5868	4.7090	4.8125	4.8918	4.9427	4.9627	4.9520
Pa	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837
RV	4.6004	4.7064	4.8133	4.9017	4.9581	4.9791	4.9671

Table 10: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase V

PHASE VI

Time(mi n)→ Compart ment↓	0.00731 8 -	0.00745 1 -	0.00758 4 -	0.00771 7 -	0.00785 0 -	0.00798 3 -	0.00811 6 -	0.00824 9 -
	0.00745 3	0.00758 6	0.00771 9	0.00784 2	0.00798 5	0.00811 8	0.00824 1	0.00838
Pressure (mm of Hg)↓								
LA	8.2782	8.3725	8.4774	8.5892	8.6944	8.7781	8.8310	8.8509
Pv	8.6574	8.6396	8.6295	8.6270	8.6312	8.6404	8.6523	8.6647
LV	8.1105	8.1644	8.2866	8.4175	8.5318	8.6197	8.6756	8.6975
Sa	128.372 8							
Sv	4.9238	4.9240	4.9241	4.9241	4.9241	4.9240	4.9239	4.9237
RA	4.9782	4.9799	4.9603	4.9350	4.9134	4.8976	4.8867	4.8798
Pa	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837
RV	4.8491	4.7880	4.7708	4.7630	4.7503	4.7340	4.7194	4.7098

Table 11: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase VI

PHASE VI (Continued)

Time(mi n)→ Compa rtment ↓	0.00838 2 -	0.00851 5 -	0.00864 8 -	0.00878 1 -	0.00891 4 -	0.00904 7 -	0.00918 0 -	0.00931 3 -
	0.00851 4	0.00864 7	0.00878 0	0.00891 3	0.00904 6	0.00917 9	0.00931 2	0.00944 5
Pressure (mm of Hg)↓								
LA	8.8419	8.8109	8.7669	8.7185	8.6735	8.6370	8.6124	8.6008
Pv	8.6757	8.6841	8.6893	8.6911	8.6900	8.6867	8.6821	8.6770
LV	8.6883	8.6553	8.6080	8.5553	8.5063	8.4664	8.4395	8.4265
Sa	128.372 8							
Sv	4.9235	4.9233	4.9231	4.9230	4.9229	4.9229	4.9229	4.9229
RA	4.8769	4.8781	4.8831	4.8911	4.9011	4.9121	4.9230	4.9329
Pa	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837
RV	4.7060	4.7073	4.7126	4.7212	4.7321	4.7440	4.7559	4.7669

Table 12: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase VI continued

PHASE VII

Time(m in)→ Compar tment↓	0.009446	0.009579	0.009712	0.009845	0.009978	0.010111	0.010244	0.010377
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0.009578	0.009711	0.009844	0.009977	0.010110	0.010243	0.010376	0.010509
	Pressure (mm of Hg)↓							
LA	8.5549	8.5681	8.6066	8.6456	8.6775	8.7017	8.7178	8.7249
Pv	8.6694	8.6631	8.6596	8.6587	8.6599	8.6625	8.6660	8.6697
LV	8.4837	8.5178	8.5458	8.5787	8.6127	8.6410	8.6596	8.6673
Sa	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728
Sv	4.9228	4.9227	4.9227	4.9228	4.9229	4.9230	4.9232	4.9233
RA	4.8993	4.8959	4.9146	4.9368	4.9523	4.9601	4.9627	4.9621
Pa	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837
RV	4.8229	4.8559	4.8701	4.8785	4.8875	4.8962	4.9018	4.9029

Table 13: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase VII

PHASE VII (Continued)

Time(min)→ Compa rtment ↓	0.010510	0.010643	0.010776	0.010909	0.011042	0.011175	0.011308	0.011441
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0.010642	0.010775	0.010908	0.011041	0.011174	0.011307	0.011440	0.011573
	Pressure (mm of Hg)↓							
LA	8.7230	8.7141	8.7011	8.6862	8.6722	8.6606	8.6522	8.6478
Pv	8.6708	8.6735	8.6752	8.6759	8.6757	8.6748	8.6734	8.6718
LV	8.6649	8.6550	8.6401	8.6235	8.6077	8.5947	8.5855	8.5807
Sa	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728
Sv	4.9234	4.9235	4.9236	4.9236	4.9236	4.9236	4.9236	4.9235
RA	4.9588	4.9531	4.9453	4.9364	4.9270	4.9183	4.9107	4.9047
Pa	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837
RV	4.8995	4.8928	4.8839	4.8739	4.8635	4.8536	4.8450	4.8384

Table 14: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase VII continued

PHASE VII (Continued)

Time(min)→ Compa rtment ↓	0.011574	0.011707	0.011840	0.011973	0.012106	0.012239	0.012372
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0.011706	0.011839	0.011972	0.012105	0.012238	0.012371	0.012504
	Pressure (mm of Hg)↓						
LA	8.6471	8.6501	8.6551	8.6612	8.6674	8.6727	8.6771
Pv	8.6703	8.6690	8.6681	8.6677	8.6677	8.6680	8.6686
LV	8.5802	8.5835	8.5892	8.5962	8.6033	8.6095	8.6143
Sa	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728
Sv	4.9234	4.9233	4.9232	4.9231	4.9230	4.9230	4.9230
RA	4.9010	4.8995	4.9002	4.9028	4.9068	4.9119	4.9175
Pa	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837
RV	4.8341	4.8323	4.8331	4.8360	4.8406	4.8463	4.8526

Table 15: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase VII continued

PHASE VII (Continued)

Time(min)→ Compa rtment ↓	0.012505- 0.012637	0.012638- 0.012770	0.012771- 0.012903	0.012904- 0.013036	0.013037- 0.013169	0.013170- 0.013302
	Pressure (mm of Hg)↓					
LA	8.6799	8.6809	8.6802	8.6778	8.6749	8.6721
Pv	8.6693	8.6700	8.6706	8.6710	8.6712	8.6713
LV	8.6172	8.6180	8.6171	8.6146	8.6115	8.6083
Sa	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728	128.3728
Sv	4.9230	4.9230	4.9230	4.9230	4.9231	4.9232
RA	4.9232	4.9282	4.9322	4.9351	4.9368	4.9371
Pa	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837	30.5837
RV	4.8590	4.8647	4.8694	4.8727	4.8747	4.8751

Table 16: Values of pressure (mm of Hg) at seven compartments during phase VII continued

The above values can be represented graphically as shown below.

Graph 1: Graphical representation of variation of pressure at eight compartments during seven phases

The actual values from the literature [1] at left atrium (LLA), left ventricle (LLV), right atrium (LRA), right ventricle (LRV) are shown in Table 17 and graphically represented in Graph 2.

TIME(Min)	PRESSURE (mm of Hg)			
	LLA	LLV	LRA	LRV
0	10	9.8	5	4.8
0.001862	10	9.8	5	4.8
0.002793	10	80	5	15
0.004256	10	120	5	25
0.006384	10	100	5	20
0.007317	10	9.8	5	4.8
0.009445	10	9.8	5	4.8
0.013302	10	9.8	5	4.8

Table 17: Literature values at four chambers of heart

Graph 2: Graphical representation of Literature values at four chambers of heart

RESULTS:

From the above tabulated tables (Tables 3 - 17), Graphs 1 and 2, the following result points are noted.

During phase I, the atrial contraction takes place. The blood pressure at the left atrium will be greater than the blood pressure of left ventricle due to which the mitral valve opens. The blood pressure of the right atrium will be more than the blood pressure of right ventricle due to which the tricuspid valve opens. However, the pressure of the left ventricle will be less than that of systemic artery so the aortic valve will be closed. Also, the pressure of the right ventricle will be less than pulmonary artery as a result of which pulmonary valve is closed. As there is no flow of blood into systemic artery and pulmonary artery, the blood pressure in systemic artery and pulmonary artery remains fairly constant. The blood pressures in pulmonary vein and left atrium are almost equal and that of systemic vein and right atrium are also almost equal.

Considering Lumped parameter model, we observe from Graph 1 that, by the end of phase I, the blood pressure in left atrium is 10.0341mm Hg which is greater than that of left ventricle which is 9.9854 mm Hg as result of which the mitral valve opens. The blood pressure in the right atrium is 4.9746 mm Hg which is greater than the blood pressure in right ventricle which is 4.9138 mm Hg due to which the tricuspid valve opens. The blood pressure in left ventricle which is 9.9854 mm Hg is, however, less than that of systemic artery which is 100 mm Hg, due to which the aortic valve closes. Also the blood pressure in the right ventricle which is 4.9138 mm Hg is less than that of pressure in systemic vein which is 4.9991 mm Hg due to which the pulmonary valve closes. We also observe that the blood pressure in systemic artery is constant at 100 mm Hg and that of pulmonary artery remains constantly at 20 mm Hg throughout phase I as there is no blood flow in these compartments during phase I. The blood pressures in pulmonary vein which is 10.0165 mm Hg and left atrium which is 10.0341

mm Hg are almost equal and that of systemic vein which is 4.9991 mm Hg is almost equal to that of right atrium which is 4.9746 mm Hg.

Also according to the literature [1] and from Graph 2 we observe that the blood pressure in left atrium which is 10 mm Hg is greater than the blood pressure variation in left ventricle which is 9.8 mm Hg due to which the mitral valve closes. The blood pressure of the right atrium which is 5 mm Hg is greater than the blood pressure of right ventricle which is 4.8 mm Hg due to which the tricuspid valve closes.

During phase II - isovolumetric contraction - the blood pressure of the left atrium is less than the left ventricle. So the mitral valve closes. The aortic valve remains closed at this juncture since the blood pressure of the left ventricle is almost equal to that of systemic artery. Also, the blood pressure of right auricle is less than the right ventricle so tricuspid valve closes and as the blood pressure of right ventricle is almost equal to pulmonary artery, the pulmonary valve closes. Thus during this phase all the four valves are closed and with no entry or exit of blood, the volume of blood in ventricle is kept constant during this phase. However, there is a slight variation in the blood pressure between left atrium and right atrium when compared with blood pressures at the end of Phase I. There is a significant increase in the pressure in left ventricle and right ventricle when compared with blood pressures at the end of Phase I as the four valves are closed in this phase. The blood pressure in systemic artery and the pulmonary artery also during this phase and is almost equal to that of left ventricle and right ventricle respectively. The blood pressure in pulmonary vein and systemic vein is almost constant in this phase.

From Lumped parameter model, we observe from Graph 1 that, by the end of phase II, the blood pressure in the left atrium which is 10.0162 mm Hg is less than the blood pressure in left ventricle which is 99.4829 mm Hg due to which the mitral valve remain closed. Also, the blood pressure in right auricle which is 4.9989 mm Hg is less than the blood pressure in right ventricle which is 19.6205 mm Hg due to which the tricuspid valve remain closed. The blood pressure in right ventricle which is 19.6205 mm Hg is almost equal to the blood pressure in pulmonary artery which is 19.3930 mm Hg due to which the pulmonary valve closes. The blood pressures in systemic artery which is 99.3399 mm Hg and pulmonary artery which is 19.3930 mm Hg also increases and is almost equal that of left ventricle which is 99.4829 mm Hg and right ventricle which is 19.6205 mm Hg respectively. The blood pressure in pulmonary vein which is 10.0187 mm Hg and systemic vein which is 4.9993 mm Hg is almost constant in phase II.

By the end of phase II, we observe from the literature values [1] and Graph 2 that, the blood pressure of the left atrium which is 10 mm Hg is less than the left ventricle which is 80 mm Hg due to which the mitral valve remains closed. Also, the blood pressure of right auricle which is 5 mm Hg is less than the right ventricle which is 15 mm Hg due to which the tricuspid valve remains closed.

During phase III, there is a rapid ejection of blood from the ventricles. This part of the cycle sees 80-85% volume of blood ejected from auricle to ventricle. As the blood pressure in the left atrium is less than the left ventricle, the mitral valve remains closed. The aorta valve opens during this phase as the blood pressure of left ventricle is greater than systemic artery. Similarly as the pressure of right atrium is less than right ventricle, the tricuspid valve is closed. Pulmonary valve opens as the blood pressure in right ventricle is greater than the pulmonary artery. Thus, during this phase the mitral and tricuspid valves are closed and the aortic and pulmonary valves are open. However, there appears to be a slight decrease in

blood pressure in left atrium and right atrium when compared with blood pressure in left atrium and right atrium during phase II. In contrast, a significant increase in blood pressure in left ventricle and right ventricle when compared with blood pressure in left ventricle and right ventricle during phase II is observed as blood is filled into the ventricles from atrium. There is also a slight decrease in blood pressure in pulmonary vein and systemic vein when compared with blood pressure in pulmonary vein and systemic vein during phase II. The blood pressure in systemic artery and pulmonary artery increase significantly when compared with blood pressure in systemic artery and pulmonary artery during phase II as respectively, the aortic valve and pulmonary valve is open in this phase.

However, when we consider the Lumped parameter model, we observe from Graph 1 that, by the end of phase III, the blood pressure in the left atrium which is 7.9242 mm Hg is less than the left ventricle which is 128.7848 mm Hg due to which the mitral valve closes. The blood pressure in left ventricle which is 128.7848 mm Hg is greater than systemic artery which is 128.3725 mm Hg due to which the aortic valve opens. The blood pressure in right atrium which is 3.3863 mm Hg is less than blood pressure in right ventricle which is 31.0069 mm Hg due to which the tricuspid valve closes. The blood pressure in right ventricle which is 31.0069 mm Hg is greater when compared with the blood pressure in pulmonary artery which is 30.5836 mm Hg due to which the pulmonary valve opens. In contrast, a significant increase in blood pressure in left ventricle which is 128.7848 mm Hg and right ventricle which is 31.0069 mm Hg is observed when compared with blood pressures in left ventricle which is 99.4829 mm Hg and right ventricle which is 19.6205 mm Hg by the end of phase II. There is also a slight decrease in pressure in pulmonary vein which is 9.1415 mm Hg and systemic vein which is 4.9453 mm Hg when compared with blood pressures in pulmonary vein which is 10.0187 mm Hg and systemic vein which is 4.9993 mm Hg by the end of phase II. The blood pressure in systemic artery which is 128.3725 mm Hg and pulmonary artery which is 30.5836 mm Hg increase significantly when compared with blood pressure in systemic artery which is 99.3399 mm Hg and pulmonary artery which is 19.3930 mm Hg by the end of Phase II as respectively the aortic and pulmonary valves opens.

From the literature values [1] and from Graph 2 we observe that, by the end of phase III, the blood pressure in the left atrium which is 10 mm Hg is less than the left ventricle which is 120 mm Hg due to which the aortic valve closes. The blood pressure in right atrium which is 5 mm Hg is less than blood pressure in right ventricle which is 25 mm Hg due to which the tricuspid valve closes. A significant increase in blood pressure in left ventricle which is 120 mm Hg and right ventricle which is 25 mm Hg is observed when compared with blood pressures in left ventricle which is 80 mm Hg and right ventricle which is 15 mm Hg by the end of phase II.

During phase IV, i.e. reduced ejection, the blood pressure between atrium and ventricle begins to equalise. In other words, the blood pressure in the left ventricle is almost equal to the blood pressure in the left auricle and the blood pressure in the right ventricle is almost equal to blood pressure in the right auricle. During this phase, most of the volume of blood that is ejected from the ventricles will now be in the pulmonary artery and the aorta. Therefore, during this period, systemic blood pressure and the pulmonary artery blood pressure are higher than the ventricular blood pressures. The ventricular blood pressure drops and aortic valve and the pulmonary valve close by the end of this phase. Also, the blood pressures in left atrium, left ventricle, right atrium and right ventricle reduce and by the end of the phase, the blood pressures at atrium and ventricle are almost equal. However, the blood pressure at systemic artery and pulmonary artery remains constant and there is a slight variation in blood pressure at pulmonary vein and systemic vein.

When we consider the Lumped parameter model, we observe from Graph 1 that, by the end of phase IV, the blood pressure in the left ventricle which is 9.0476 mm Hg is almost equal to the blood pressure in the left auricle which is 8.9745 mm Hg and the blood pressure in the right ventricle which is 4.5015 mm Hg is almost equal to blood pressure in the right auricle which is 4.4577 mm Hg as a result respectively the mitral and tricuspid valve remains closed. During this period, systemic artery blood pressure which is 128.373 mm Hg and the pulmonary artery blood pressure which is 30.5837 mm Hg are higher than the blood pressures at left ventricle which is 9.0476 mm Hg and right ventricle which is 4.5015 mm Hg respectively due to which the aorta and pulmonary valves close by the end of this phase. However, the blood pressure at systemic artery which is 128.373 mm Hg and pulmonary artery which is 30.5837 mm Hg remains constant and there is a slight variation in pressure at pulmonary vein which is 8.8202 mm Hg and systemic vein which is 4.9259 mm Hg when compared with blood pressures at pulmonary vein which is 9.1415 mm Hg and systemic vein which is 4.9453 mm Hg by the end of phase III.

During reduced ejection, the blood pressure in the left ventricle is almost equal to the blood pressure in the left auricle due to which the mitral valve is closed and the blood pressure in the right ventricle is almost equal to blood pressure in the right auricle due to which the tricuspid valve is closed. However when we observe the literature values [1] and Graph 2, we observe that, by the end of phase IV the blood pressure at left ventricle which is 100 mm Hg is greater than the blood pressure in the left auricle which is 10 mm Hg and the blood pressure in the right ventricle which is 20 mm Hg is greater than the blood pressure in the right auricle which is 5 mm Hg which indicates that the aortic valve and pulmonary valve have to open respectively.

Phase V is similar to the first phase. Instead of isometric contraction, there will be isovolumetric relaxation. During this phase there is less blood pressure in the left ventricle than in the systemic artery due to which the aortic valve closes and less blood pressure in right ventricle than in pulmonary artery due to which the pulmonary valve closes. The blood pressures at atrium will be almost equal to that in ventricles. With this higher pressure in systemic artery and pulmonary artery, the mitral valve and the tricuspid valve opens. This leads to next phase of rapid ventricular filling. From Table 10, we observe that the blood pressure at left atrium is almost equal to blood pressure at left ventricle and the blood pressure at right atrium is almost equal to blood pressure at right ventricle due to which the mitral and tricuspid valve remain closed respectively. The blood pressure at systemic artery is greater than the left ventricle, the aortic valve is closed and as the blood in the systemic vein is greater than right ventricle, the pulmonary valve is closed. Thus during this phase all the four valves will be closed.

By the end of phase V, when we consider the Lumped parameter model, we observe from Graph 1 that, there is less blood pressure in the left ventricle which is 8.1097 mm Hg than in the systemic artery which is 128.3728 mm Hg due to which the aortic valve closes and less blood pressure in right ventricle which is 4.9671 mm Hg than in pulmonary artery which is 30.5837 mm Hg due to which the pulmonary valve is closed. The blood pressures at right atrium which is 4.9520 mm Hg will be almost equal to that in right ventricle which is 4.5671 mm Hg due to which the tricuspid valve remains closed. The blood pressures at left atrium which is 8.2006 mm Hg will be almost equal to that in left ventricle which is 8.1907 mm Hg due to which the mitral valve remains closed.

Considering the literature values [1], we observe from Graph 2 that, by the end of phase IV, the blood pressures at right atrium which is 5 mm Hg will be almost equal to that in right

ventricle which is 4.8 mm Hg which results in closure of tricuspid valve. The blood pressures at left atrium which is 10 mm Hg will be almost equal to that in left ventricle which is 9.8 mm Hg which results in closure of mitral valve.

During Phase VI, approximately two-thirds of the blood volume is passively moved from the atria into the ventricles. As the blood pressure at left atrium is greater than the blood pressure at left ventricle, the mitral valve opens and the blood flows from left atrium to left ventricle. Similarly, as the blood pressure at right atrium is greater than the blood pressure at right ventricle, the tricuspid valve opens and the blood flows from right atrium to right ventricle. However, as the blood pressure at left ventricle is less than blood pressure at systemic artery, the aortic valve remains closed and as the blood pressure at right ventricle is less than blood pressure at pulmonary artery, the pulmonary valve remains closed. From Tables 11 and 12, it is observed that the atrium pressure is greater than that of ventricle and as the consequence of this the mitral and tricuspid valves open and blood starts flowing from atrium to ventricle.

Similarly, it is also observed from the above tables that the blood pressure at systemic artery and pulmonary artery is more than at the left ventricle and right ventricle respectively, due to which the aortic valve and pulmonary valve remains closed. The blood pressures at systemic vein and pulmonary vein remains almost constant. To summarise, during rapid filling, the mitral and tricuspid valves are open and aortic and pulmonary valve is closed.

While observing the Lumped parameter model and Graph 1 we notice that, by the end of phase VI, the blood pressure at left atrium which is 8.6008 mm Hg is greater than the blood pressure at left ventricle which is 8.4265 mm Hg due to which the mitral valve is open. The blood pressure at right atrium which is 4.9329 mm Hg is greater than the blood pressure at right ventricle which is 4.7669 mm Hg due to which the tricuspid valve is open. However, the blood pressure at left ventricle which is 8.4265 mm Hg is less than blood pressure at systemic artery which is 128.3728 mm Hg due to which the aortic valve is closed. The blood pressure at right ventricle which is 4.7669 mm Hg is less than blood pressure at pulmonary artery which is 30.5837 mm Hg due to which the pulmonary valve is closed.

The literature values [1] and, also, Graph 2 indicate that, by the end of phase VI, the blood pressure at left atrium which is 10 mm Hg is greater than the blood pressure at left ventricle which is 9.8 mm Hg due to which the mitral valve is open. The blood pressure at right atrium which is 5 mm Hg is greater than the blood pressure at right ventricle which is 4.8 mm Hg due to which the tricuspid valve is open.

Phase VII is also called the slow or passive filling phase. During this phase, more atrial blood volume goes into the ventricle. The remaining one-third of volume of blood is pushed into the ventricles. At one point there is an equal pressure in the atria and the ventricles is observed. By the end of this phase, more volume of blood is in the ventricles than in atria as a result of which the mitral and tricuspid valves begin to close. Once the mitral and tricuspid valves close, the heart begins the next cardiac cycle. Since the pressure at systemic artery is more than that at the left ventricle, the aortic valve is closed. As the pressure at pulmonary artery is more than that of right ventricle the pulmonary valve is closed. From Tables 13-16, one can observe that the blood pressure at atria is greater than the blood pressure at ventricles due to which the mitral and tricuspid valves are open. The blood pressures at systemic artery are greater than at left atrium and the blood pressure at pulmonary artery is greater than right ventricle due to which the aortic and pulmonary valves are closed.

While analyzing using Lumped parameter model, we observe from Graph 1 that, by the end of phase VII, the pressure at left atrium which is 8.6721 mm Hg is almost equal to pressure at

left ventricle which is 8.6083 mm Hg so the mitral valve begins to close during this phase and the pressure at right atrium which is 4.9371 mm Hg is almost equal to pressure at right ventricle which is 4.8751 mm Hg due to which the tricuspid valve begins to close during this phase. The pressure at systemic artery which is 128.3728 mm Hg is more than that at the left ventricle which is 8.6083 mm Hg. The pressure at pulmonary artery which is 30.5837 mm Hg is more than that of right ventricle which is 4.8751 mm Hg.

While from the literature values [1], we observe from Graph 2 that, by the end of phase VII, the pressure at left atrium which is 10 mm Hg is almost equal to pressure at left ventricle which is 9.8 mm Hg due to which the mitral valve begins to close and the pressure at right atrium which is 5 mm Hg is almost equal to pressure at right ventricle which is 4.8 mm Hg due to which the tricuspid valve begins to close.

CONCLUSION:

Thus, one can conclude that the cardiac cycle consists of nearly synchronized activity of the atria and ventricles. The sequence is essentially the same for the right and left sides of the heart. However, to make the study more clear the cardiac cycle has been divided into seven phases. The purpose of this work was to discuss the important phases of the cardiac cycle and analyse the variation of blood pressure at each compartment using Lumped Parameter Method. From the above mentioned tables, Tables 3 to 16, it is clear that the cardiac cycle is a continuous cycle of pressure changes and blood flow. From Graphs 1 and 2 it is clear that the result got by modeling using Lumped Parameter method is very close to the literature values. Thus the use of this equivalent electronic circuit of cardiovascular system is useful for studying of whole cardiovascular system on ground i.e., at sea level.

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